

Improvement of cardiovascular stent design through advanced numerical simulation

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Abstract

The project aims to demonstrate the capability of advanced numerical simulation based on Finite Element modelling to investigate transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI) designs, deployment geometries and the stent's capacity to be loaded and unloaded. Numerical simulation appears as a cheap option to study the devices' behaviour and the different factors that may influence it. In this study, it is proposed as a support and guidance for the design process. The focus is given to the assessment of the loading capacity of the stent into the device, deployment of the stent and interactions with the deployment device. These studies require large computational models which are also highly non-linear. In that sense, high performance computing can help to reduce computational time and increase the number of cases to study without increasing expensive experimental setup.

The objective of this study is to provide a tool to simulate TAVI behaviour and help the SME to optimise the design in the future. In particular, this project aims at investigating how different modelling strategies in terms of material model, geometric properties and discretisation procedures can impact analysis results. In order to do so the Alya code, developed at Barcelona Supercomputing Center, is adapted to perform the simulations.

This project has been developed as collaboration between LVD Biotech and the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC) within the SHAPE programme of PRACE.

1. Introduction

Aortic stenosis is the most common form of valvular heart disease in the industrialized world. Nowadays transcatheter aortic valve implantation (TAVI) is the preferred treatment to treat aortic valve stenosis for older patients, due to the high risk of a surgical intervention. Despite this technique reporting satisfactory outcomes with respect to standard therapies, complications such as paravalvular leakage or aortic root rupture have been shown in a considerable number of patients.

In the last years, personalised medicine and patient-specific computational simulations have emerged as powerful tools to obtain predictive information about the behaviour of the device, either in the delivery process or after expansion. Computer simulations can be used to examine the device performance either in isolation to determine its structural integrity or when deployed to reconstruct the loading forces induced by the stent on the aortic valvular complex, as well as to investigate the interaction between the device and the tissue. Stents may be self-expanding or balloon expandable and can be made of various materials including stainless steel, Cobalt Chromium, Nitinol or polymers. The proliferation of stent designs carries difficult problems to the clinicians and manufacturers in order to choose the optimal device design for each case. Each different stent design has a different structural behaviour and the mechanical characteristics also influence the result. Analysing these factors experimentally can be economically prohibitive, because of the prohibitive costs of the materials and the amount of mechanical experimental cases that will be required in order to obtain the optimal model. Computer simulations based on Finite Element methods present as a less costly option to support the design process, moreover, they also allow to focus on specific areas of interest.

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Finite element study of TAVI is an active topic of research. Different modelling strategies have been proposed in order to investigate the feasibility of TAVI in patient specific morphologies, as well as the behaviour of the device itself. The two most common TAVI devices are the balloon expandable Edward Sapien and the self-expandable Medtronic corevalve. This work focuses on the self-expandable device, made of Nitinol. In the proposed project, simulation is presented as a tool for designing medical devices, in particular, a stent structure for an aortic valve and its interaction with the delivery system. A stent is mesh structure placed into an artery of blood vessel (or a native valve) to keep a blocked lumen open. For the self-expandable configuration, the stent is first loaded in the delivery system into a cover sheath and it is placed in the desired position through the anatomy. Then the cover sheath is removed and hence the stent recovers its initial shape, given initially through a forming shape process (a heating process), thanks to the superelastic properties of the Nitinol material. In contrast to balloon expandable stents, the stents that are here considered are self-expandable, profiting from the same memory alloy material properties in order to recover the optimal form once placed within the artery.

Computer-based simulations are employed to reconstruct the loading forces induced by the stent, as well as to evaluate the radial force produced by the self-expandable device in order to optimise its design. The complexity of these simulations and the amount of parameters that remain uncertain and influence the simulation outcomes makes the validation a crucial issue, still being a bottleneck of the process. Hence, the aim of the present work is a first step, in which the focus is given to investigate the design parameters and modelling strategies that may affect the behaviour of the device. Due to the complexity of the simulations in terms of geometrical and mathematical non-linearities (for instance, large deformations are present and the material model itself is highly non-linear), large computational resources are needed, especially for a second stage of the investigation, in which more detailed discretisations will be used and the more sophisticated material model of Nitinol will be used for the simulation.

There are many stents available in today's market. It is crucial to understand its design's effect to develop new models that behave better for each disease and cheaper. The proper design of the stent is one of the current bottlenecks for the SME. To optimise stent capabilities, the current design activity is aimed at improving uniform deployment and maximal radial force. Simulations allow to study the stent deployment and then its mechanical properties. They will provide the SME a new tool to support the design process and validate their product before going to the manufacturing process and to the market.

2. Modelling approach

2.1 Modelling equations

The motion of the stent is governed by a second-order partial differential equation

$$\nabla \underline{\underline{\sigma}} + \vec{b}_0 = \rho_0 \ddot{\vec{u}}(t) \quad \forall x \in B_0$$

where ρ_0 is the density of the material, \vec{b}_0 is the body force vector, u is the displacement field and $\underline{\underline{\sigma}}$ is the Cauchy stress tensor. B_0 is the domain in the reference (undeformed) configuration. In order to solve the equation for stresses and displacements in the stent, the constitutive equation of the material must be determined. The constitutive equation relates the stresses and the strains. If the constitutive equation is known, then it is possible to solve the governing equations subjected to specific boundary conditions using the finite element method. Determining the constitutive equation can be a difficult task because of nonlinearity, non-uniformity and anisotropy of the material. In general, the material model is defined using the energy function W to define the constitutive equation. The second Piola-Kirchhoff stress tensor, S_{ij} , commonly used to formulate the material response, is related to W by

$$S_{ij} = \frac{\partial W}{\partial E_{ij}}$$

where E_{ij} is the Green's strain tensor.

A Finite Element discretisation is used, by applying the spatial discretisation to the weak form of the governing equations, see [1] [2] for the standard procedure. A set of nonlinear ordinary differential equations is obtained:

$$\underline{\underline{M}} \ddot{\vec{u}}(t) + \vec{f}_{int}(\vec{u}(t)) - \vec{f}_{ext}(t) + \vec{f}_c(\vec{u}(t)) = 0$$

where $\underline{\underline{M}}$ is the mass matrix, \vec{f}_c represents the contact force vector, \vec{f}_{int} the internal force vector and \vec{f}_{ext} the external force vector.

2.2 Contact constraints in large deformations

In order to define a finite strain initial boundary value problem, the contact conditions governing the response of the contact surface are needed. Consider a point $X \in \Gamma_c^{(1)}$ in one surface, and a point $Y \in \Gamma_c^{(2)}$ in the other contact surface. The current position for both points is expressed by means of a transformation function, $x = \vec{\varphi}_t^1(X)$ and $y = \vec{\varphi}_t^2(Y)$. The gap function between both contact points is defined as:

$$g(X, t) = -\vec{\nu} \cdot (\vec{\varphi}_t^1(X) - \vec{\varphi}_t^2(\bar{Y}))$$

where $\vec{\nu}$ denotes the outward unit normal to the contact surface Γ_c^2 at point y and \bar{Y} is the closest contact point projection in an Euclidean sense of the point x onto the opposite surface Γ_c^2 .

The contact traction is assumed to be positive in compression, and it is defined by considering the nodal component of the traction to the surface, that is:

$$t_N = \vec{t}^1(X) \cdot \vec{\nu}$$

The contact conditions that relate the traction and the gap follow the Kuhn-Tucker optimality conditions, i.e.:

$$t_N \geq 0, \quad g \leq 0, \quad t_N g = 0$$

which must hold for all points in the contact surface of the deformable body.

In this work, a unilateral frictional contact and hard normal contact is proposed [3]. Instead of modelling and discretising the rigid body structure, which is usually used as a reference for the detection of contact, it is supplied by a parametric function defining the surface of the rigid body. Since contact is a boundary problem, only the surface of the body is needed, and at the same time, only the nodes lying on the contact surface of the deformable body need to be specified in the contact algorithm.

Contact between the stent and the rigid body (usually a cylinder for crimping or expansion, or a mandrel for deployment) is activated and de-activated in a dynamic way using a Dirichlet-Neumann type parallel algorithm for the numerical solution of nonlinear frictional contact problems. The algorithm avoids the use of Lagrange multipliers, hence avoiding the introduction of additional degrees of freedom. This approach puts special focus on its computational implementation and the use of parallel resources. In this algorithm the bodies in contact are treated separately, in a segregated way. This fact will allow to use contact without constructing the rigid body, that is, the rigid body will be replaced by a geometrical function that defines the surface of the body, hence avoiding the computational memory waste and effort of having a second body and discretising it. The coupling between the rigid and the deformable body is performed through boundary conditions transfer at the contact nodes.

The main idea of the Dirichlet-Neumann method is to replace the geometrical constraints due to normal and frictional contact by partial Dirichlet-Neumann boundary conditions in the case of unilateral contact with an arbitrary rigid surface. The geometrical constraints due to normal contact are imposed by means of Multi-Point constraints, while the friction is imposed as a tangential force applied in the opposite direction of the sliding node.

2.3 Boundary conditions and loading

The loading conditions depend on the kind of operation to be modelled. Basically they are divided in three groups: loading of the stent, deployment of the stent (stent release for implantation) and resheath of the stent into the delivery device. The loading step involves reducing the diameter several times compared to its original one in order to load it. The deployment step consists on expanding the stent to simulate the stent release for implantation. Finally, the resheath step refers to fold the stent into the cover sheath. The three steps require the definition of boundary conditions and contact interactions, as detailed below. Appropriate boundary conditions are a crucial aspect of the simulation, and each of the scenarios requires different assumptions in order to ensure an accurate representation of the geometry and the real experimental conditions.

Loading simulation

In order to simulate the loading, the stent is reduced in diameter by simulating a crimping process. During the loading process the contact and pressure over the stent is made on the exterior surface, simulating a cylindrical rigid body (the “crimper”) and the boundary conditions are set at each time step. The radius of the cylinder is defined as a parametric function, which computationally is a space and time function, $R(r, t)$, depending on the radial coordinate and the time. The space time function is constrained axially and radially on a cylindrical coordinate system along the longitudinal axis of the stent. Boundary conditions are then applied to radially contract the cylinder until reaching the radius given by the function, simulating hence the action of a cylindrical rigid body and compressing the stent to the desired diameter. The contact nodes of the stent are set free in the longitudinal and tangential direction, hence imposing also a frictional contact in order to ensure a well posed problem. The contact nodes of the stent are updated and the contact constraints are enforced by means of the Dirichlet-Neumann type parallel algorithm [3].

Deployment simulation

In order to perform the simulation of the crimped stent up to its final shape, a/the contact algorithm is used to expand the device to the desired shape. The contact and pressure of the rigid body is made on the interior surface of the stent following the same ideas as loading, but in the opposite direction. The space and time function defines the radius of the expander, usually modelled as a balloon, which increases along the simulation.

In this work, the expansion of the stent is performed to simulate the stent forming step. The stent is expanded onto a mandrel in a multi-step heat-treat process in order to retain memory of the shape. It is worth noting that the shape of the stent to be manufactured is not necessarily cylindrical. In that sense, the way of imposing the contact by means of a space and time function, allows to define the new geometry of the stent by just defining the shape of the surface, either by means of a continuous function or by means of a discrete set of points. In terms of geometry and computational memory it gives more flexibility since the discretisation and meshing process of the rigid body is avoided. For instance, in standard procedure, this discretisation is made by using shell elements, which imply a different treatment in a Finite Element code. Moreover, meshing a curved geometry sometimes is not straightforward.

Resheath simulation

The deployment of the stent into a given device is a bit more complex. Experimentally, the stent is tied on the end-struts and then pulled into the delivery device. In this case, the delivery device plays the role of the rigid body, but in contrast with the loading and deployment cases, the radius of the rigid body is constant, hence, the function defining the device surface is constant. In terms of modelling and simulation, since the stent is pulled in order to be introduced inside the device, the movement of the stent is imposed not only in the radial direction, but also in the axial direction. In the axial direction it is a Dirichlet boundary condition, but in the radial direction the displacement is given by the contact with the deployment device. This fact has two important consequences in the modelling. First, the function defining the radius and shape of the deployment device depends not only on the radial coordinate, but also on the axial coordinate. In this case, the rigid body corresponds to the deployment device, which in order to allow a smooth deployment and avoid convergence problems, takes a funnel form in one of its ends. In the proposed contact algorithm, a curved spline defines the funnel in the entrance and a cylinder for the rest of the device. Second, the contact nodes follow a dynamic process, which means that at each time step of the simulation the nodes of the deformable body (the stent) have to be identified and projected onto the rigid body surface, defined by a parametric function. It is worth noting that since neither the device nor the stent are perfect cylinders, the projection and the imposed displacement in the contact nodes and has to be done in a proper coordinate system which is perpendicular to the surface. Hence, in this case, the coordinate system has to be defined for each node at each time step.

Moreover, due to the difference of the stent radius and device one, deformations of more than 300% of the original geometry arise, hence adding a modelling and computational challenge to the problem, because non-linearities and large deformations are copped. Despite with the crimping and expansion cases the final deformed shape also presents a reduction or increase of the initial radius of these magnitudes, the process of crimping makes this reduction gradually. In contrast, the introduction of the expanded stent into the deployment device forces a 300% deformation in one step, giving rise to high non-linearities and convergence issues.

3. Case study

An example application is used in the simulation of implanted stent devices. The following steps are the standard ones to characterise the response of Nitinol stents:

- 1) Generate a 3D model from a 2D drawing, where a geometry transformation is necessary to generate the 3D model of the smallest repeatable segment.
- 2) The initial analysis simulates the shape setting step, in which the expansion of the stent is typically performed using a mandrel and may include intermediate steps along the way until achieving the final expanded shape.
- 3) After expansion, the obtained deformed geometry is recovered and treated in order to obtain a stress free state to be used for the stent implantation step.
- 4) The stent is load into the deployment device, a sheath, typically at a similar diameter to the original one, which eventually has a curved entrance in order to facilitate crimping. A rigid cylinder contact is used for this stage of the analysis.
- 5) Release the stent from the delivery device simulates deployment.

The provided stent has a length of 36.8 mm and inner and exterior radius of 2.0 mm and 2.995 mm, respectively and a non-symmetric number of struts along its length, that is, it has less struts at one end. Figure 1 shows the provided crimped stent by the SME.

Figure 1: Original stent of radius 2.995 mm and length 36.8 mm.

The material used is a superelastic material which tries to imitate the martensite phase of the Nitinol, in order to facilitate large deformations. For the simulations, as a first attempt, an hyperelastic constitutive model is used. Table 1 shows the material and geometrical properties of the stent.

Case	Density (g/cm ³)	E (GPa)	nu	Length (mm)	Outer radius (mm)	Inner radius (mm)
Figure 1	6.45	30	0.33	36.8	2.995	2.0

Table 1: Geometrical and material properties of the stent

The study performed here consists on the three intermediate steps, since the 3D geometry is given by the SME. In the first phase of the study, the stent forming step, the stent is expanded onto a given shape, the mandrel, in order

to be manufactured. Then, in order to obtain a stress free state, computationally the nodal coordinates are extracted and the full displacement value is added to each node, updating the coordinates. Finally, the stent is loaded into the deployment device of cylindrical shape. In order to facilitate the deployment, the device has a curved entrance. The last step, the release of the stent is not considered in this study.

3.1 Expansion of the stent using a mandrel (shape setting)

Experimentally the first phase is carried out in several steps: first the stent is heated up to a temperature such that it can be deformed and adapted to a first range of the mandrel. The shape of the stent is set by heat treating and then, after cooling, the stent is stress-free. This process is repeated several times until it achieves the desired shape. Computationally this process can be done in a single step and without the need to manufacture the mandrel, by properly defining the shape of the mandrel with a geometrical function and then expand the stent until it contacts the surface defined by the function. The maximum radius of the expanded stent is approximately 14 mm, which is almost 5 times bigger than the original one.

3.2 Deployment of the device into the sheath

For the deployment of the stent into the device, a shape of the cover sheath is also given by the SME. The provided shape is defined by colinear 5 points, hence several splines can fit. One of the bottlenecks of the study is the optimisation of this shape. As a first attempt, a second order spline curve is defined for one end of the device. Experimentally, the stent is tied on the final struts and pulled to fit into the device, which ends as a cylinder of radius 3 mm. It is especially relevant to ensure convergence and a smooth deployment of the stent to select enough number of nodes of the struts for the Dirichlet condition. Actually, appropriate boundary conditions are one of the bottlenecks of the numerical simulation of this problem.

4. Results

A computational mesh of 167,809 tetrahedra is used as a first approach. The computational domain is simplified in order to reduce the computational cost of the simulation but without a significant loss of accuracy on the results. Due to the large deformations and non-linearities the computational cost of the simulation increases notably, especially because of the amount of iterations required to converge at each time step. The numerical simulations are conducted with the multiphysics code Alya developed at BSC [2]. The simulations were conducted in the supercomputer Marenostrum IV with 4 nodes (192 cores) spending about 2 CPU hours for each simulation.

For the first phase of the study, simulating the forming process of the stent, the parametric definition of the mandrel is first set. In order to simplify the process, a conical shape has been selected. Then the final deformed shape is obtained in a single simulation, using an implicit time integration step, but avoiding restarting and resetting stresses in intermediate steps. Since only the final expanded shape is needed (see Figure 3), it is not necessary to move the stent axially along the full mandrel, hence, simplifying also the numerical simulation. CPU time was 4.5 minutes. Figure 2 shows the final shape of the stent in cylindrical coordinates. It is worth noting that the final deformed geometry is not symmetrical, neither cylindrical, due to deformation between the struts. The results obtained from this first step can help the manufacturing process in the sense that many shapes of the expanded stent can be tested

and the stent can be enforced up to a maximum radius without the need of manufacturing the mandrel, neither the stent itself.

Figure 2: Expanded stent onto a conical shape, units are in mm.

For the second phase of the study, the implantation of the stent, the mesh obtained from the previous simulation is set as the initial configuration in a stress-free state. First, a radial compression on the Dirichlet nodes (the “pulling nodes” of the struts) is performed and afterwards, an axial displacement is applied on these nodes to introduce the stent into the device. At this stage, the shape of the deployment device becomes relevant, since large deformations of the order of 300% arise at a single time step, just at the time that the stent contacts the device. In order to allow a smooth transition and avoid undesirable results, the deployment device should be designed with an initial curved shape, simulating a funnel. As stated before, this is a current bottleneck, not only for the simulation itself, but also to the manufacturing process of the device itself, that can be significantly costly for the SME. In that sense, numerical simulations can help to the design and manufacturing process of stenting in two ways: they are first used to provide an overview of deployment process and the structural performance of the stent to evaluate the quality of the design. Secondly, the optimal shape of the deployment device can be improved by evaluating the influence of the shape of the funnel into the deployment stage.

As explained in Section 2.3, the contact algorithm is dynamic in the sense that, as the stent is crimped into the deployment device, the contact nodes are being activated and deactivated at each time step, depending on the gap function given by the parametric function of the rigid body and the distance to the node. Figure 3 shows four different snapshots of the process and the contact nodes detected.

Figure 3: Sequence of the crimping process of the stent in to the deployment device. In red, the contact nodes at the different steps are shown. From left to right and top and bottom: times $t=0.5s$, $t=1.5s$, $t=2.5s$ and $t=3.0s$.

For the study, different shapes of the funnel have been evaluated, changing some of the parameters of influence, such as the length of the funnel, the curvature or the initial diameter. Several simulations have been performed in order to test the influence of these parameters and find the optimal shape. Each of these simulations have been performed in Marenstrum IV with 4 nodes (192 cores) and the adapted Alya code. An implicit time integration scheme with a Rayleigh damping model with parameters $a = 1000$ and $b = 0$ (1) is used in order to avoid dynamical effects and add some stabilisation. It is worth to remark that the results are not very sensitive to changes in the mass matrix coefficient, a , which can vary between 1000 and 10000 with very similar damping action. The momentum equation is solved using first a Conjugate Gradient solver for the compression step, and a GMRES solver with a Block Diagonal preconditioner when the stent contacts the cylinder. The time step used is 5×10^{-3} seconds. Each of the simulations takes approximately 1:30 h CPU time.

The optimal funnel shape has been found to be a second order spline of 4 mm length of the funnel and an initial radius of 4.5 mm. However, since many parameters influence the outcome, a more detailed study should be considered. Moreover, it can be noticed from Figure 3 that due to the inertial force and residual stresses coming from the initial compression step, the final radius of the stent is not uniform, neither the final shape is cylindrical, in the sense that at one end of the stent the radius becomes smaller than the radius of the deployment device and the contact with the cylinder is lost. A detailed study of the influence of the boundary conditions should be done.

Regarding convergence of large deformation problems, Alya has shown to behave as expected, showing convergence in displacement, force and energy up to the required precision, which in this case was 10^{-5} for displacement. As expected, force convergence is always more restrictive and difficult to achieve, however, as shown in Figure the behaviour for both values show the same behaviour and remains constant for all the deployment process.

Figure 4: Displacement, force and energy residual for deployment process.

5. PRACE cooperation and benefits for the SME

The Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe (PRACE) provided the expert support to adapt the Alya code for this application and the BSC Marenostrum IV supercomputer is used for the simulations. The 200 hours assigned to the Computer Applications for Science and Engineering (CASE) group of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center have not fully been employed due to technical problems arising from the complexity of the simulations themselves. However, the use of the supercomputing facilities has been a key piece in the study because of the time-consuming simulations and the large number of runs performed to find the optimal configuration of the problem.

The results of this SHAPE project are not deterministic, but they provide support and a guidance to the company in the development of the design process of the devices. Once the optimal parameters are set, it is expected to perform a full simulation with a refined mesh in order to improve accuracy of the results. The use of an HPC-code, Alya, which is also open to be modified, becomes a benefit in these kind of simulations, which present high convergence problems due to non-linearities and large deformations. Moreover, the possibility of performing a wide sequence of parallel runs in a short time gives the SME an extra tool in the design process. In order to obtain more definitive results that can help to the decision process of the SME, more resources are needed.

The main difficulties faced were the adaption of the initial project to the needs of the SME. The initial objective was to study the CoCr and Nitinol material behaviour, but after a first initial meeting, the SME and BSC discovered that computer modelling can play an important role in the design of the devices, both the TAVI and the deployment devices, and can support the process by modelling the process of stent manufacturing and delivering.

Another difficulty arising from the current situation was the communication of the progress of the project and results of the work by the BSC researchers, due to the technical problems of modelling the experimental setup. The best way to cope with this difficulty was to make periodic reports with the problems found and the results. Moreover, due to the complexity of the experiments and the impossibility of face-to-face interviews to set the proper conditions of the experiments, communication was slower.

6. Conclusions

Computer modelling can play an important role in the design of medical devices and in the investigation of their mechanics and structural behaviour. The Alya code has been adapted in order to simulate the physical response of the loading step of the stent into the deployment device, using a contact algorithm and large deformations approach. A validation process needs to be defined in order to get conclusions. Despite more resources are

required in order to obtain useful predictions for the SME and the code can be improved, the present project has developed a tool which is expected to provide support and guidance to the SME in the design process of the physical response of the stent. The SHAPE project has guided the SME to the HPC and opens up using HPC resources to support and help the design process.

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